

as reagents for vanadium by substituting groups on the phenyl ring of the acyl part, *N*-benzyl-2-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid (B-2-CBHA) was prepared and reported elsewhere¹. Literature shows that the analytical potentialities of this hydroxamic acid are still unexplored. The present communication, reports the efficacy of this compound (reagent) in the extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v).

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorbance. A 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution was prepared in alcohol-free chloroform. An aqueous solution of vanadium(v) was prepared from ammonium metavanadate (A.R.) and standardised titrimetrically². All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

General procedure for extraction of V: To a suitable aliquot of vanadium solution (43.7–200 µg of V^V) aqueous HCl was added to maintain a volume of 10–15 ml and acid concentration 4.5 M. A 0.1% solution (5 ml) of the reagent in chloroform was then added to it and the contents were shaken for about 2 min. The reddish violet chloroform layer was extracted and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. Extraction was repeated (2–3 times) with successive volumes of the reagent solution (total 10–15 ml). The combined extract was made upto 25 ml with chloroform and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 510 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The reddish violet complex extracted into chloroform at 4.5 M HCl showed an absorbance maximum at 510 nm. The optimum acidity range of extraction for the complex was found to be 3.0–7.0 M HCl; the acidity was always adjusted to 4.5 M for all measurements. The volume of the aqueous phase may be varied from 10 to 30 ml without affecting the final absorbance. Chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent for extraction of the complex. The complex had the same absorbance value for at least a week when stored in a cool dark place. Thereafter, the colour intensity decreased but the λ_{\max} remained unchanged. Colour of the complex attained maximum value when the reagent concentration was 20 times in molar excess. Beer's law was obeyed at 510 nm over the concentration range 2.0–8.5 ppm V^V. The optimum working range based on Sandell's recommendation³ was found to be 2.4–7.2 ppm. The sensitivity of the colour reaction was 0.010 µg cm⁻² at 510 nm with molar absorptivity $(4.88 \pm 0.06) \times 10^3$ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

In the study of the effect of diverse ions, varying amounts of diverse ions were mixed with the vanadium solution containing 87.4 µg of V^V and the colour was developed as described earlier.

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium with *N*-Benzyl-2-chlorobenzohydroxamic Acid

N. K. KSHATRIYA

Research and Control Laboratory,

Bharat Aluminium Co. Ltd.,

Korba-495 684

and

BASANT R. SAHU*

C.M.D.P.G. College, Bilaspur-495 001

Manuscript received 3 October 1989, revised 2 April 1991,
accepted 6 May 1991

IN an attempt to improve the sensitivity and selectivity of *N*-benzyl substituted hydroxamic acids

The tolerance limit of ions causing an error of 2% are shown in parenthesis (in mg); Pr^{III} (137.5), Th^{IV} (55), U^{VI} (55), Zr^{IV} (75), Zn^{II} (20), Ti^{IV} (3.75), Mo^{VI} (45), Mg^{II} (137.5), Al^{III} (45), Co^{II} (20), Ni^{II} (25), Fe^{III} (25), Cr^{III} (37.5), Cu^{II} (50), Cd^{II} (90), Li^{III} (75), Bi^{III} (50), Mn^{II} (27.5), acetate (62.5), chloride (125) and fluoride (20). The procedure when employed for large amounts of Pb^{II} and Ti^{III} present with V^V, gave precipitate which absorbs V^V. This reduces the extraction of vanadium and low results are obtained. Repeated extraction and prolonged agitation was found to be satisfactory. W^{VI} gave a precipitate of hydrated tungstic acid with HCl. This includes V^V for coprecipitation. Repeated extraction with 0.3% reagent solution recovered the coprecipitated V^V. Ce^{IV} and Mo^{VI} caused serious interference to PBHA and many other *N*-arylhydroxamic acids when used for the photometric determination of V^V. The reagent was found not to give any coloured extracts with Ce^{IV}, Mo^{VI} and Zr^{IV} under the experimental conditions and extracted V^V selectively. All the major impurities of Bayer liquor, aluminium oxide and aluminium did not interfere with the determination. Analysis of V in various samples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM (V) IN STEELS AND BAYER PROCESS PRODUCTS

Sample	V %	V ₂ O ₅ g dm ⁻³	V ₂ O ₅ %
(i) Steel (B.C.S.)			
(a) Low alloy (no. 252)	0.457 (0.460) ^a	—	—
(b) High speed (no. 241/1)	1.568 (1.570) ^a	—	—
(ii) Bayer liquors			
(a) Pregnant liquor	—	2.19 (2.17) ^b	—
(b) Spent liquor	—	1.96 (2.00) ^b	—
(iii) Aluminium oxide			
(a) Sample no. 1	—	—	0.0082 (0.0080) ^b
(b) Sample no. 2	—	—	0.010 (0.0095) ^b
(iv) Primary aluminium			
(a) Sample no. 1	0.0052 (0.0048) ^c	—	—
(b) Sample no. 2	0.0042 (0.0040) ^c	—	—

^aCertified value. ^bBy phosphotungstate method. ^cBy emission spectrometer.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.K.K.) express his sincere thanks to Dr. S. K. Mukherjee, Mr. O. N. Sharma and Mrs. K. R. Nambiar for encouragement and to Balco Management for permission to publish this paper.

References

1. B. R. SAHU and U. TANDON, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1983, 28, 433.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, London, 1961, pp. 265, 646.
3. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd ed., Interscience, New York, 1959.